

РОЛЬ МУДРЕЦОВ В ВОСПИТАНИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ В ДУХЕ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье утверждается, что толерантность молодежи в современных условиях связана с уровнем осведомленности об общечеловеческих социальных процессах, проблемах, которые интересуют или беспокоят человечество, знанием программ, проектов, решений, принимаемых международными организациями, таких как как ООН, ЮНЕСКО, ЮНИСЕФ, и активное участие в их реализации.

Ключевые слова: Толерантность, молодежь, справедливость, честность, религия, вера, вера, человечность, правдивость.

THE ROLE OF SAGES IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF TOLERANCE

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ABSTRACT

In the article, it is stated that the tolerance of young people in the present conditions is related to the level of awareness of universal social processes, problems that interest or bother humanity, knowledge of programs, projects, decisions adopted by international organizations such as the UN, UNESCO, UNICEF, and active participation in their implementation.

Keywords: Tolerance, youth, justice, honesty, religion, faith, belief, humanitarianism, truthfulness.

YOSHLARIMIZNI BAG‘RIKENGLIK RUHIDA TABIYALASHDA ULUG‘ ALLOMALAR MEROSINING AHAMIYATI

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ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada Hozirgi sharoitda yoshlarning tolerantligi umuminsoniy ijtimoiy jarayonlardan, insoniyatni qiziqtirayotgan yoki bezovta qilayotgan muammolardan xabardorlik darajasi, BMT, YuNESKO, YuNISEF kabi xalqaro tashkilotlar qabul qilgan dasturlarni, loyihalarni, qarorlarni bilishi, ularni amalga oshirishda faol qatnashishi bilan ham muayyan darajada bog‘liqligi bayon qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Bag‘rikenglik, yoshlar, adolat, insof, diyonat, imon, e’tiqod, insonparvarlik, haqiqatparvarlik.

The issue of morality, which has been an integral part of our social consciousness in our nation since ancient times, is expressed in a unique way in the life and work of great scholars, in their works that made a turning point in the history of mankind.

Indeed, in the views of the great thinkers who lived in our country, they understood such qualities as valuing man as the master of all beings, spiritual perfection and maturity, justice, honesty, religion, faith, belief, humanity, truthfulness and tolerance as the main criteria of their scientific and practical activities.

In the spiritual and moral improvement of young people, we can take as a basis the spiritual and scientific heritage of our great thinkers Abu Nasr Farabi, Al-Khorazmi, Beruni, Abu Ali Ibn Sina, Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, who are the roots of our spiritual heritage. With this, together with the formation and development of the scientific outlook, spiritual and moral feelings in young people, we will achieve a deep study of our history, pride in it, and respect for our spiritual and moral values.

Today, tolerance is one of the urgent problems facing the peoples of the whole world. First of all, let’s clarify the concept of tolerance itself. Tolerance, that is, the term tolerance, is the readiness to accept the opinion, point of view, culture, worldview, faith of each person as they are. It is the desire of different people to live together in harmony.

The term "tolerance" is derived from the Latin word "tolerantia" and means tolerance for the thoughts, beliefs and actions of others.

Tolerance is one of the highest virtues of the Uzbek people, and our parents have taught us to be respectful, considerate and forgiving towards the people around us from

a young age, raising us in this spirit. In fact, if a person shows respect for the people around him, is considerate and forgiving, this quality creates conditions for him to work with others and live in harmony.

In the current conditions, the tolerance of young people is also related to the level of awareness of universal social processes, problems that interest or bother humanity, knowledge of programs, projects, decisions adopted by international organizations such as the UN, UNESCO, UNICEF, and active participation in their implementation. The adoption of the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" by UNESCO on November 16, 1995 is a clear proof that tolerance is one of the most pressing problems today.

In fact, in many countries of the world, due to the impatience of young people, there are cases of disrespecting parents and adults, joining various extremist groups, and committing various terrorist acts. In order to prevent such unpleasant situations, we must educate our youth in the spirit of tolerance and patience.

There are many noble, tolerant and courageous people among our ancestors. In particular, when it comes to tolerance, it is permissible to tell young people a story that happened to the great thinker Jalaluddin Rumi. One day, His Holiness Rumi meets the Pope, the priestly leader of the Christians. Even though he is not a priest, His Holiness Rumi is the first to bow to him. In the interpretation of His Holiness Rumi, this was considered a simple, humane rule; pop, in turn, pays homage to Rumi. His Holiness Rumi bowed again for the second time. Pop, for his part, does not leave it unanswered. This mutual respect - a show of respect, a kind of "humanity competition" is repeated several times. In the end, His Holiness Rumi will win. The disciples of Maulana, who were watching this situation, were shocked. "What if this person we know - the leader of the Muslims - His Holiness Jalaluddin Rumi? After all, is it permissible to pay so much respect to a stranger?"

His Holiness Rumi, who entered the circle of disciples, saw their amazement and said: "We should not lose sight of them in patience and tolerance. We will not give this high rank to outsiders. After all, our prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him, taught us to respect the human race. is circumcision."

The nobleness, goodness, patience, compromise, forgiveness, benevolence, generosity, open-heartedness, kindness, which are truly characteristic of the Uzbek people, were reflected again in the period of our country's independence. Speaking about the main idea of our national ideology and the ideas that will help us realize this idea, our ultimate goal - to build a free and prosperous Motherland, to build a free and prosperous life, the President emphasized that the idea of religious tolerance is of special importance among them. The idea of religious tolerance means that people of different religious beliefs live together in one land, one country, in the path of noble

ideas and intentions. Representatives of more than 136 nationalities live in our country. A free civil society, a secular state is being established in Uzbekistan. Our state has created equal opportunities for all religions and all faith holders on a legal basis.

In order to cooperate with representatives of other nations and peoples, a representative of each nation must know and respect the culture, language, and customs of that nation, and be able to share in their pain. Only in this way can he find his way into the hearts of other people.

However, a person should not become a victim of events happening around him, saying that he will be tolerant. In such cases, tolerance appears as a negative trait, which is a product of human indulgence. In many cases, people who are overly cheerful and anxious are considered "cowards" and can be easily broken. It is worth emphasizing once again that everyone should be tolerant, that is, forgiving and civilized. Because tolerance is something that depends on human nature. God created man with the same nature.

Among our national values, faith, religion, patriotism, honesty, kindness, generosity, and tolerance, that is, tolerance in a broad sense, are important in educating the young generation. From a young age, the child grows up together with representatives of different nationalities. Parents, teachers educate young people in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland, kindness, humanity, respect and, at the same time, tolerance. Currently, in addition to the level of education and profession of our youth, it is necessary to give great importance to educating them in the spirit of national tolerance and moral qualities in harmony with our national values.

The culture of tolerance prepares the ground for harmony between nationalities, ethnic groups, peoples, international cooperation, and pluralism in socio-cultural life. Especially in multinational countries, cultural tolerance is an imperative for socio-cultural development and the formation of an international environment in the country. 136 nations, peoples and ethnic groups live in Uzbekistan. Each of them has its own culture, tradition, language of communication, way of thinking and lifestyle, holidays and ceremonies. The diversity and pluralism of cultures make the common socio-cultural life beautiful, charming, interesting, inter-ethnic relations and communication alive, because only lively contacts give dynamism to the socio-cultural life, reflect the current problems, ideas, values of the time. Today, our youth receives various information every day through the mass media and the Internet. However, we are not in favor of banning young people what to see and what not to see, and generally one-sided education. Because we are building an open and free democratic society. We must educate young people in such a way that they do not fall into bad influences in any situation, "we imagine the future of our country not wrapped in our own shell, but deeply absorbing universal and democratic values. We see our perspective in

liberalizing state and social governance, introducing human rights and freedoms, diversity of opinions into our lives using the experience of developed countries. Today, we support an enlightened world, a peaceful, free and prosperous life, and mutually beneficial cooperation with the international community." However, we must protect our children from spreading ideas of immorality, violence, individualism, and egocentrism, which are called "mass culture" and have a negative effect on the spirituality of our youth.

Therefore, in order to educate our youth in the spirit of love for the Motherland, loyalty to our history, our holy religion, and to be tolerant, it is necessary to strengthen ideological immunity and strengthen their humanity. Humanity is one of the important conditions of tolerance and includes the qualities of respect, trust, pure heart, sincerity, humility, and purity towards the members of society. Also, studying the spirituality of our great ancestors in the past, which they contributed to the development of world science and culture, "high moral feelings and concepts such as honor, shame, chastity, which were formed and polished in the thinking of our ancestors for centuries and thousands of years. It is the main duty of us intellectuals to raise tolerance.

In today's ideologically globalized society, in the process of globalization of "mass cultures", young people brought up in the spirit of tolerance protect themselves from spiritual threats with their moral highness, putting Christian dignity at a high level, and also treat the people around them with love. From this point of view, it is natural that the field of comprehensive philosophical knowledge is a unique factor in the implementation of this task.

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